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Use of Telemedicine in Bangladesh: Current Status and Future Prospects

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ABSTRACT

Health and medical systems are poised to benefit significantly from advances in digital health. One of the digitalization that has gained great attention in Bangladesh over the last several years is mobile health (mHealth). In developing nations such as Bangladesh, the application of mobile health technologies in the health industry has immense potential to improve the quality, accessibility, and cost of healthcare. A significant percentage of people in the developing world, particularly those who live in rural or remote areas, still do not have or have only access to essential services. The business, social, and non-governmental organizations have all committed to investing a large amount of money in the development of mobile healthcare infrastructure throughout the United States. In Bangladesh, the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in healthcare, particularly mobile health, is rapidly rising. But what is the present situation of health, or what is the best course of action for its further development in the future? Providing an introduction of mobile health, identifying unmet needs for health, outlining motion wellbeing in Bangladesh, and analyzing ethical issues and hurdles in the growth of mobile health are the goals of this study. The results of our study demonstrated that, while e-health in Bangladesh remains a problem, it is doable. Given the view of the existing circumstances and problems, greater progress is required in several areas within the field of mHealth. The findings of this study will be beneficial to a wide range of stakeholders. to make informed choices about e-services- services and capital growth in Bangladesh's health sector.

Keywords

Bangladesh, telemedicine, developing country

Introduction

The world is transitioning from a manufacturing-based economy to a service-based economy. 1 Healthcare system is one of the most rapidly increasing sectors of the economy, and its expansion may be sustained if the influence of the sector's expansion on the performance of stakeholders is carefully considered. 2 In Furthermore, when there is a high prevalence of disabling illness, it is impossible to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. 3,4,5 Health-care reform is both a development issue and a healthcare issue, and both must be addressed. 6 However, as a result of a lethal combination of limited access to care, inconsistent quality, and increased costs, this sector has been facing significant difficulties. 7,8 Using mobile communications in this context has the potential to significantly improve the accessibility, affordability, and accessibility of health delivery by providing it more readily available. 9 In reaction to the delivery challenge, mobile health approaches have been introduced and implemented To order to provide healthcare services, several organizations have proposed and deployed mobile health technology. 10,11 Digital health, also known as health or mHealth, has, on the other hand, been rapidly expanding in Western and developed countries in recent years. Below is an annual graph representation of the increased number of internet users in Bangladesh.

Fig. 1: Telehealth Market by Region (USD Billion)/ Source: Markets and Markets

Fig. 2: Number of internet users in Bangladesh has increased every year

(<https://www.lightcastlebd.com/insights/2020/07/telemedicine-for-bangladesh-bridging-the-doctor-patient-gap/>)

Fig. 3: Telemedicine Market Growth (in USD Millions) / Source: Grand View Research

Telemedicine for Bangladesh: Bridging the Doctor-Patient Gap - Light Castle Partners

Approximately 85 percent to 97 percent of worldwide people now have access to a mobile phone, according to estimates. 12,13 It is predicted that by 2021, the number of available smartphones will approach 3 billion, according to the new zoo's World Market Report in 2018 (available here). Mobile phone penetration in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) is 82 percent (in highest in the nation), while in Bangladesh it is only 5.4 percent. It received a great deal of attention for providing high-quality healthcare services. A new field of medicine called mobile health (mHealth) has evolved as a result of the rapid increase in the use of mobile technologies and their connection to obtain health-related data. Effective implementation of 14mHealth has been achieved in developed countries to provide better access to healthcare services (Chowdhury & Ahmed,2021).

This growth in mHealth applications is due to the wide range of functions that smartphones, tablets, and other devices have to offer. 17 To address the issue of limited access to health care and the necessity for cost-cutting, mHealth is being considered here. 18 mHealth is a viable,scalable, and dependable solution because of its widespread availability and ubiquity. a delivery platform for healthcare. This ICT windfall has also had an enormous impact on the healthcare industry in underdeveloped countries. eHealth 24 As a result of the anticipated benefits of mHealth services number of initiatives have been proposed and implemented around the world. 25 To achieve sustainable development goals, Bangladesh, like some other industrialized and developing economies, is grappling with limited resources and a vast population to ensure that everyone has access to affordable and accessible healthcare. Bangladesh is among the few countries worldwide where all residents have access to free medical care from the country's public hospitals. It is estimated that Bangladesh has 607 government hospitals, witUpazila490 Upazila and 1450 union-level health care facilities, as well as one secondary or tertiary level hospital. 26 In addition, there are 5023 private hospitals in Bangladesh.

There are 20,603 doctors registered with the DGHS. Despite this, Bangladesh has been ranked as one of the 57 nations on earth with a major deficit of health personnel (fewer than 1.26 clinicians, midwifery per 1000 inhabitants) and operating rooms (4 per 10,000). 27 Furthermore, because of the country's high population density and insufficient healthcare infrastructure, it is difficult to provide affordable and adequate health care. 28 Bangladesh's overall medical service consumption and demand are low compared to other developing countries. 29,30 Different private health organizations have worked hard to improve their healthcare to patients by collaborating with the state through ICT-enabled healthcare services (Sanzogni & Sandhu,2019).

Since there are not enough assets, the government has started a new era in the medical sector by ICT Implementation for the delivery of health services, especially m - health, which is being promoted in Bangladesh to provide affordable, egalitarian, high-quality health care. As a result of mHealth, healthcare services are expected to improve. The Bangladeshi government has developed a partnership with development partners, corporate groups, and non-governmental organizations in the aim to enhance the quality, effectiveness, and safety of eHealth services in the nation (NGOs). 32 However, the majority of past study has solely focused on the use of healthcare in Bangladesh first from viewpoint of the users themselves. 33 Until now, there has not been a comprehensive examination of Bangladesh's current position and its growth potential. That's why we're doing this investigation.

Each of the six sections of this paper has its heading: (1) an overview of mobile health; (2) needs for mobile health; (3) main mobile health product or technology in Bangladesh; and (4) digital and mobile health services; (5) ethical issues in mobile health development; and conclusion. MHealth stands for mobile health and refers to the use of devices such as smartphones, tablets, wireless devices, and digital assistants in the medical profession and the maintenance of public health records (PDAs).

Electronic health care services 34. An important part of electronic health is the rapidly growing field of mobile health. 35 mHealth is defined as the use of the Online and other technologies to disseminate health information and services. MHealth also refers to the use of comparatively tiny, laptops or communication devices to meet the public healthcare or health data needs of consumers. 37 37 mHealth refers to the delivery of studies that looked at services via mobile technologies (Chowdhury & Ahmed,2021). This study focused solely on the use of smartphones to provide healthcare services.

When it comes to delivering health care via mobile platforms, telemedicine refers to the use of clinical involvement. eHealth refers to the use of ICT in the delivery of healthcare services. When it comes to healthcare, mHealth refers to the usage of mobile devices that are capable of storing and sending informational-time in real-time among patients and healthcare providers. Portable electronic devices can be used to communicate health information via a wireless or other wireless channel of ground stations using mHealth. As a result of 38mHealth, health systems are being transformed by improving access, cutting costs, delivering timelier and so much, and encouraging consumer-centered health care very well. 39 This term was used in another recent study, which defined mHealth as the utilization of a mobile phone and its different functions to provide various healthcare solutions. E-Health's 40mHealth component has emerged, but it does not completely replace it. It offers highly customized health care services. 41 mHealth services include a number of distinct features that are shown in the following table 01.

Concerns regarding a shortage of healthcare services in Bangladesh could be alleviated by Bangladesh's rapid growth in communication and information technology (ICT). Mobile phone service providers in Bangladesh include Grameen Phone (GP); Banglalink; Robi; Airtel; City cell; and Tele talk. In addition, 98% of the population of Bangladesh had access to mobile phones of some sort. 40 Worldwide, 96% of people own a cell device, with 128 percent of those in richer nations and 89 percent of those in poorer countries having access to one. 50 As of January 2018, Bangladesh had 147 million active internet subscribers, growing at a pace of 13.8% annually, and 9.05 crore online services.

Health care is still an issue in Bangladesh even though many mHealth efforts have been deployed there. Mobile health apps can potentially be used to help Bangladesh surpass this Barr however the most of Bangladeshis also are unfamiliar with this option health52,13 ehealth is in its childhood in Bangladesh's healthcare sector. mHealth services were first introduced in the mid-1990s. 53 As early as July 1999, the Swinfen Charitable Foundation in the United Kingdom set up a mHealth link between CRP in Dhaka and the Royal Navy Center in Haslar, the United Kingdom. 54 TRCL and Grameen Phone partnered together in 2006 to establish mobile connections for customers or subscribers, with a call center in the U. S. as the hub. For a little fee, many other mobile phone providers provide access to medical counseling and prescription to millions of their customers. Projects in Bangladesh include health services, disease monitoring and routine data collection for promoting health and illness prevention. Agents and non-governmental organizations are involved in the current projects (NGOs).

In 2011, the World Health Assembly included Bangladesh in a list of 15 countries that were using smart phone health to raise health awareness. 56 Although 98 percent of the people WHO targeted for health education were reached via SMS, no messages were available in the recipients' native language, according to WHO. 56 MHealth knowledge repository includes a few examples of mHealth-related projects. All the projects listed in the country were financed mostly by the private sector and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), higher education institutions, and other finance providers. In Bangladesh, there are an estimated 225 eHealth and mobile health apps (Zabeen and Bhowmik,2021).

There have been many mHealth initiatives and programs since 1990. Mobile telephone infrastructures and text messaging technologies were used successfully by TRCL (Telehealth Reference Center Ltd.) in 2005. The "AMCARE" chronic disease management service was established by TRCL in Bangladesh at the end of the year 2009. TRCL DPMS and Mobile Apps were added in the initial phase of implementation. There followed a pilot project to integrate rural doctors under TRCL's medical call center network financed by DFID (UK) in subsequent years. An additional medical customer support service for Bangladeshi ex-pats is now available through TRCLI in Singapore. 58 Direct tele-consultations to government doctors, Messaging solutions for patient management, and communication with personnel have been introduced by the government health services. There is little doubt that mHealth will be a developing platform for medicinal services in Bangladesh, but the adoption of these services by the general public remains a challenge.

Materials and methods

Initiatives undertaken in government hospitals

Since the first mHealth project was launched in 1998, the percentage of innovations has grown exponentially. New research shows that 26 projects are currently underway in the field of mobile health, all of which aim to provide health services and/or manage health data. 63 Every district and Upazila hospital in Bangladesh has been equipped with mHealth, a small rural call center that provides citizens with 24-hour medical advice. It has opened doors, especially for those who are less fortunate.

Rural residents have access to medical advice. 63 March 2010 marked the beginning of Bangladesh's Pregnancy Care Advice via SMS service. Increasing the health of newborns and mothers is expected to facilitate the achievement of MDGs 4 and 5. 64 A Day later, at the Regional Digital Innovation Fair, the Telemedicine facility was officially launched. A total of 10 new telemedicine clinics opened in ten various hospitals in 2012, according to a press release. It was established in 2013 that 10 new telemedicine centers were opened at 10 different hospitals. 65 There were 25 Telemedicine Centers established on January 10, 2015, by the Information & Communication Technology (ICT) division, as a portion of all its 'Info Sarkar' program. to provide healthcare to rural residents 11 medical institutions and organizations will provide free consultations and treatment to patients in rural places.

Tele products that appeal, mobile ophthalmoscopes, tele spirometers, mobile temperature sensors, tele Electrocardiography, tele BPG machines, tele diagnostic devices, and conferencing microscopes, along with

many other modern tele-gadgets, were sent to 25 upazila care complexes to pass these Telemedicine Stations, together with eight other types of modern facilities. Mobile phones are also being used in healthcare in Bangladesh as part of the country's 2021 "Digital Bangladesh" plan, and the government is encouraging their use. Introduction and implementation of various information and communications systems (ICT) is known as eHealth in Bangladesh. When it comes to electronic health records, the terms "eHealth Record" and "medical Record" are interchangeable. Apollo Hospitals Dhaka doctors are now available to patients through this service, which can be accessed at local data centers (Chowdhury & Ahmed,2021).

Telemedicine is a service that allows doctors to consult with patients In community clinics, telemedicine is available. Union Information and Telemedicine Service is a telemedicine service provided by the Union Information and Telemedicine Service.Center for Customer Service Complaints or ideas can be sent by SMS. SMS-based prenatal care counseling SMS-based health statistics Computerization of hospitals Population Health Registry on the Internet Databases of Human Resources Dental Medical Admission Tests are processed online.The ADP Progress Monitoring System allows you to keep track of your progress. In the Health Service, GIS Software for Managing Schedules SMS in bulk

Initiatives undertaken in the private hospitals

A lot of medical centers in Dhaka City today use their own databases system to keep track of their patient's health records. The private sector's involvement in health activities in Bangladesh is unusual. Even though mHealth has been provided by a diverse range of telecommunications firms, non-governmental organizations, and other private groups (Sanzogni & Sandhu,2019).

In Bangladesh, private clinics have taken on most of the mHealth projects, according to the World Bank. In addition to mobile telephone operators, for-profit and non-profit organizations, producers and distribution companies of health-related commodities, delivering services NGOs that are incorporating information and communications technologies (ICTs) into their work, and academic research departments are now included among the NGOs working in the eHealth and mHealth fields. A diverse variety of m-health and health innovations have been made possible thanks to financing from a multitude of different.

Tele meeting

Apollo Healthcare facilities Dhaka has established a tele meeting service for patients from all across the country, according to the company. This is a feature that lets patients perform a video conversations with concerned Consultants over the internet using the Skype application. it is necessary for them Using this service, which real is available at various information centers, patients can now consult with an Apollo Healthcare Dhaka doctor without having to travel.

Health Information Lines

As part of a collaboration with the Telemedicine Resource Center, Grameenphone was one of Bangladesh's leading mobile phone service providers, developed the state's first telephone health counseling line in 2006.

Collaboration with service providers is being pursued. In collaborative efforts with the non-profit Diabetic Organization of Bangladesh, TRCL founded AAM CARE a subscription-based organization. This is done that geared to use a phone call center to inspire complying with diabetes management procedures and provide a link to skilled and experienced doctors and nurses. AM CARE was launched in 2009. (DAB).

Health Information Technology (IT) Programs in Private Sector and Non-Organizations

The private industry and mobile health programs in Bangladesh are interesting because various telecom companies, non-governmental organizations, and other commercial groups play a significant role in mHealth. Upon that, several non-governmental organizations (NGOs), including BRAC, Sajida Fund, and D.Net, expressed an interest in eHealth. Many private companies grew interested in telehealth and/or health records systems following that, and implemented them in their clinics and hospitals. Around March 2012 and March 2013, as per a study conducted by the Global Centre for diarrheal Study, Bangladesh (ICDDR,B), an average of 26 projects (either pilot or full-scale training programs) with indirectly or directly links to electronic health records (e-HR) and mobile health applications (mHealth) were implemented in Bangladesh, with four general populace, eighteen personal, and four non-governmental institutions (NGOs) participating. A maternity and neonatal healthcare information system developed in conjunction with Johns Hopkins State college, m-Care connects rural hospital patients and institutions with expectant mothers and their babies in Bangladesh, allowing them to receive better care (Sanzogni & Sandhu, 2019)

MAMA Bangladesh is a non-profit organization that promotes maternal and infant health. Global alliance dedicated to leveraging mobile technologies to enhance mother and child health, the Mobility Alliance for Maternity Action (MAMA) was established in 2009.

Websites and text messages as sources of health-related information

According to the Bangladesh Telecommunications Regulatory Board (BTRC), mobile phone operators are required to distribute the government's SMS messages at no cost to the state or mobile phone subscribers in the country.

Aponjon provides a mobile health service.

The Aponjon mHealth program, a USAID effort in Bangladesh sponsored by the Mobility Alliance for Maternity Action (MAMA) that had undergone a successful test, was given a soft launch after a successful test.

Manosh's Imagination:

With the assistance of community health professionals, Manoshi was able to gain significant traction in her efforts to assist underprivileged women during pregnancy, labor, and neonatal care. As part of a Manoshi (MNCH Urban) Technology, the initiative is undergoing testing in urban slums. The program's goal is to digitize health care services by gathering, storing, and preserving household data, which will eventually result real-time digital database in a real-time digital databases.

Mobile health provides the following health services:

The Grameenphone company established "789 Health Care services" for all of its subscribers in Bangladesh, while Banglalink just announced the launch of "Health link Service." For all Robi customers, dial 789 to connect with live contact center professionals who can assist them with any health-related questions.

Mobile Health Services and Ethical Issues

While mobile healthcare systems have the potential to improve the quality of care and the overall quality of life in patients and their family, they may also raise new issues about patient security and privacy problems. These issues must be addressed before the widespread adoption of mobile health technology in healthcare. Foreorder for the mobile health system to function, three components must be in place: wearable sensors, a smartphone, and a web server. 68 Patient's health information systems are synced with test results kept on smartphones, which are then transferred to an internet service site. It will be possible for the patient's doctor to assess the finding and make rapid remarks to the patient when they have been told of them. A violation of privacy or the misuse of data can occur at any time. Those who suffer from physical or mental illnesses, on the other side, are often reluctant to report their symptoms. Furthermore, the vast majority of people suffering from severe psychological disorders who require medical attention are still forced to be admitted against their own will by members of their families. 69 Furthermore, based on one research, 55 percent of applications shared some or all of this information with third-party organizations. 70 EveryEach and every health service that is provided through a mobile phone is immediately documented. Consequently, if this occurs, the confidentiality of the user may be threatened.

Regulatory Policies and Issues

In the realm of healthcare, where daily health is on the line, it is extremely delicate. To ensure that medical services are offered in a safe environment, precise methods and standards must be developed and adhered to. Otherwise, severe repercussions may emerge from the use of such a system. Despite the fact that Bangladesh's government enacted a national information and communications technology strategy in 2009, it has yet to get an influence on hospitals. Bangladesh's regulatory and legal structure has not yet been upgraded to meet the growing demands of the world's electronic manufacturing industry, which is a concern. The use of email in government offices, on the other hand, has no official significance and cannot be lawfully regarded as an authorized mode of communication. There are no effective anti-cybercrime or electronic authenticating laws in place in the United States. 72 Bangladesh adopted a National Strategy on Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) in 2002, to implement a nationwide Infrastructure by 2006. 73 There is a lot of optimism about Bangladesh's telecom sector because it has the potential to address a range of development concerns, particularly those related to health. This is demonstrated by two recent papers, the National Information Policy-2009⁷⁴ and the Bangladesh Draft Plan Should address 2010–2021, which are also available online (Planning Commission 2010). The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) has developed draft proposals for Bangladesh e-health guidelines as well as an interoperability architecture to reduce duplication of effort and facilitate linkages among health systems. So, to date, the

standards have primarily addressed data collection and administration (Chowdhury & Ahmed,2021). In terms of developing a legal framework, much less headway has been accomplished. So, date, the standards have primarily addressed data collection and administration.

However, when it comes to nongovernmental organizations, the development of a regulatory framework has met with substantially less success. The kind of services that can be provided by a corporation, the qualifications of those who offer advise, company ownership, and pricing practices are all subject to debate at the moment (Zabeen and Bhowmik,2021). According to the worldwide mHealth sector, establishing linkages between the telecommunications and health industries is one of the most difficult obstacles to offering these services to a wider audience. 75 Callers to the designated phone numbers can be made free of charge by the government in order to make this mHealth program more available to the masses.

Challenges

In Bangladesh, inexperience, a lack of English language proficiency, a loss of faith, and technological incapability are among the obstacles to using mobile health services (mHealth services). 16 Following the country of Bangladesh's huge investments in health communication and information technologies, the country's mobile health (mHealth) system is still in its embryonic stages. is confronted with a wide range of difficulties and limits 75 These include issues such as defining the service, keeping order across different organizations, maintaining financial viability, ensuring technical staff is available, and a lack of common specifications for health communication and information technologies, which creates problems in data sharing and management among various databases as well as interoperability, to name a few examples. Low-speed internet connectivity in many remote locations, as well as the high cost of infrastructures and integrated software innovation, all pose significant barriers to the widespread adoption of mHealth services. The promotion and implementation of mobile health in Bangladesh, as in other poor nations, is beset by several difficulties. This investigation has discovered. A few of the most serious threats and challenges to the implementation of mobile health in the industrialized regions are as follows:

Insufficient ICT network - There is an inadequacy IT strategy, as well as a lack of knowledge among government officials and citizens. Human resources are insufficient. Information technology systems that are excessively complicated, Lack of coordination, inadequate IT literacy, a scarcity of IT training, expensive expenses, and a decrease in Internet access liability are all issues that need to be addressed. Inadequate educational opportunities, Essential services are difficult to obtain, and there is a scarcity of information, along with other issues. The (NHP)-2011 listed the following issues as being of particular concern: 1) A poor management structure, a scarcity of materials, and an absence of healthcare improvement; 2) a low awareness and good service in the scenario of mothers and child care; and 3) a lack of public consciousness and good services in the case of motherhood and child treatment are all issues that must be addressed. The failure to adequately manage contagious diseases; the failure to adequately regulate and prevent the spread of new diseases and viruses; and the failure to adequately manage contagious diseases.

The lack of sufficient resources to combat infections that have harmful environmental consequences, such as dengue disease and malaria, is a major concern. Management of human resources and development are not up to standard. The absence of health-related research is a major concern. Bangladesh's health services sector is facing a number of challenges as it moves toward digitization. 75 A number of difficulties have been identified based on previous investigations (Chowdhury & Ahmed,2021).

Conclusion

Specifically, the goal of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of mHealth-related publications released since 1998 in order to have an understanding of the current situation of mHealth services, as well as difficulties and opportunities for the future growth of mHealth services. The findings are presented in a variety of formats, including the current status, issues, policy proposals, and regulation, to name a few examples. As with many other initiatives, private institutions such as hospital, telecommunications corporations, and non-governmental agencies (NGOs) are working to deliver diverse mobile health services to all individuals. Both the government are committed to using information and communications technology (ICT) to improve health-care delivery. On the subject of technical preparedness, it has been observed that the society is at least partially prepared. However, inequity was discovered in the areas of human resource preparation and technical ready capacities. As a result of these data, it is concluded that the overall situation of the digital medical services industry in Bangladesh is dismal. The recipients of healthcare services are completely unaware of this healthcare service innovation. Although the use of mobile medical services in Bangladesh has increased significantly in recent years, it remains a small proportion of the total range of health services offered, despite the rapid rise of different wireless commercial services.

Recommendations for the Future and Limitations in Bangladesh, the use of mobile health technologies is still very much in infancy. It is therefore necessary to provide top priority to the creation of local eHealth solutions, as well as adoption research and usability studies. The findings of this study have provided some recommendations for establishing an effective mHealth system. Policymakers and government bodies in Bangladesh should work together to build a clear national health plan in order to assist the adoption of digital revolution in the health-care industry. As soon as feasible, detailed suggestions for the Healthcare Information Architecture's standards and interoperability protocols should be developed and published. According to the conclusions of this study, substantial preparation and planning are required for Bangladesh in order to effectively execute eHealth and mHealth operations on a large scale.

Implications for Theory and Practice

A variety of theories 'health implications can be drawn from the findings. To the aimed to contribute, this will be the first research to provide an analytical explanation of the existing condition, obstacles, and potential direction of mHealth in the country of Bengal. The findings of this study contribute to the body of information about the condition of mHealth in developing nations, particularly Bangladesh, and in Bangladesh. In planning their campaigns, legislators and providers of mHealth services will find the results

of this study to be extremely valuable. Mobile health (mHealth) can be considered one of the prospective and supportive systems within the healthcare sectors of developing countries, to improve the goal of improving the access, effectiveness, performance, and reliability of the business and clinical procedures used by medical institutions, practitioners, patients, and customers in order to cheer up the health of patients and consumers. Medical device regulators should examine other techniques for assessing the safety and reliability of mHealth services (Sanzogni & Sandhu, 2019). There must be in strong direction and supportive policy measures to older to realize the full potential of mobile health. A rising ICT-based health care service that is easy to use and freely accessible across the country must be developed by service providers. Additional research is needed to fully understand the true potential of technology. The development of various regulations for eHealth governance should be the primary focus of study on the incorporation of eHealth and mHealth further into the Bangladesh healthcare system. b If you're interested in studying eHealth, mHealth, telehealth, telehealth, telemedicine, and videoconferencing in a separate study, you can do it as well.

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